

RESEARCH ARTICLE

**Toxicity, transfer and metabolization of the pyrethroid insecticides
cypermethrin and deltamethrin by reared black soldier fly larvae**

N. Meijer^{1}, L. Zoet², D. Rijkers¹, R. Nijssen¹, M. Willemsen¹, P. Zomer¹ and H.J. van der Fels-
Klerx¹*

¹Wageningen Food Safety Research (WFSR), Wageningen University and Research, Akkermaalsbos 2, 6708 WB Wageningen, The Netherlands; ²Bestico B.V., Veilingweg 6, 2651 BE Berkel en Rodenrijs, The Netherlands; *nathan.meijer@wur.nl

Supplementary material

TABLE S1 LC-HRMS settings for FS/DDMS2 en FS/vDIA

FS/DDA methode	
Scan event:	Full scan
Scan range:	110-1100 m/z
Resolution:	70,000 FWHM @ m/z 200
AGC:	1,000,000
Max inj. Time:	200 msec
Sheath gas flow:	48
Aux gas flow:	11
Sweep gas flow rate:	2.25
Spray voltage (kV):	3.5 (ESI+) / 2.5 (ESI-)
Capillary temp °C:	256
S-lens RF level:	50
Aux gas heater temp (°C):	410
Spectrum data type	Profile mode
Scan event:	DDA top 5
Resolution:	17,500 FWHM @ m/z 200
Stepped NCE	30, 80
Dynamic exclusion	10 s
FS/DIA methode	
Scan event:	Full scan
Scan range:	110-1100 m/z
Resolution:	70,000 FWHM @ m/z 200
AGC:	1,000,000

Max inj. Time:	200 msec
Sheath gas flow:	48
Aux gas flow:	11
Sweep gas flow rate:	2.25
Spray voltage (kV):	3.5 (ESI+) / 2.5 (ESI-)
Capillary temp °C:	256
S-lens RF level:	50
Aux gas heater temp (°C):	410
Spectrum data type	Profile mode
Scan event:	DIA
Resolution:	35,000 FWHM @ m/z 200
Stepped NCE:	30, 80
nr of DIA events:	5
Mass range DIA 1:	95-205
Mass range DIA 2:	195-305
Mass range DIA 3:	295-405
Mass range DIA 4:	395-505
Mass range DIA 5:	495-1005

TABLE S2 Overview of performance of larvae: yield (g), survival (%), and mean individual larval weight (mg) for tested treatments containing cypermethrin, deltamethrin, and/or piperonyl butoxide (PBO) at indicated concentrations in dry feed (mg/kg). Arithmetic mean and standard deviation for n = 6 samples per treatment

Number	Treatment and concentration (mg/kg)	Yield (g)	Survival (%)	Mean individual larval weight (mg)
1	Control	9.77 ± 0.36	99.0 ± 3.7	197.5 ± 7.8
2	Solvent control	9.12 ± 0.68	99.3 ± 1.6	183.8 ± 15.4
3	PBO (20.0)	9.75 ± 0.21	100.3 ± 1.5	194.4 ± 5.4
4	Cypermethrin (1.0)	8.43 ± 0.42	91.7 ± 6.1	184.1 ± 6.0
5	Cypermethrin (2.0)	6.35 ± 0.83	86.7 ± 8.6	146.1 ± 5.4
6	Cypermethrin (1.0) + PBO (10.)	8.02 ± 0.60	95.3 ± 4.3	168.1 ± 6.9
7	Cypermethrin (2.0) + PBO (20.)	4.25 ± 0.62	85.7 ± 12.9	99.4 ± 5.8
8	Deltamethrin (0.06)	8.75 ± 0.47	95.0 ± 5.0	184.6 ± 13.3
9	Deltamethrin (0.13)	7.23 ± 1.68	88.0 ± 7.8	163.0 ± 26.9
10	Deltamethrin (0.25)	4.18 ± 0.55	64.7 ± 8.9	129.7 ± 11.9
11	Deltamethrin (0.50)	2.11 ± 0.61	57.7 ± 9.2	72.4 ± 12.3
12	Deltamethrin (1.00)	0.62 ± 0.08	40.3 ± 7,5	31.3 ± 4.1

13	Deltamethrin (0.13) + PBO (1.25)	6.44 ± 0.77	77.0 ± 6.8	167.6 ± 14.9
14	Deltamethrin (0.25) + PBO (2.50)	3.77 ± 1.02	62.0 ± 14.3	121.0 ± 17.2
15	Deltamethrin (0.50) + PBO (5.00)	1.32 ± 0.15	51.0 ± 5.0	52.2 ± 7.4